

THE EFFECT OF *USHIR MALAHAR* IN THE MANAGEMENT OF *PARIKARTIKA* (FISSURE-IN-ANO): A CASE REPORT

Dr. Komal Gutte*¹, Dr. D.W. Lilke², Dr. Vitthal Kasse³, Dr. Onkar Jadhav⁴

¹PG Scholar in Shalya Tantra Dept, Government Ayurved College and Hospital Dharashiv.

²HOD and Associate Professor of Shalya Tantra Dept, Government Ayurved College and Hospital, Dharashiv.

³Assistant Professor of Shalya Tantra Dept, Government Ayurved College and Hospital, Dharashiv.

⁴PG Scholar in Shalya Tantra Dept, Government Ayurved College and Hospital Dharashiv.

Article Received on 01 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 21 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 01 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18802721>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Komal Gutte

PG Scholar in Shalya Tantra Dept,
Government Ayurved College and
Hospital Dharashiv.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Komal Gutte*¹, Dr. D.W. Lilke², Dr. Vitthal Kasse³, Dr. Onkar Jadhav⁴. (2026). The Effect Of Ushir Malahar In The Management Of Parikartika (Fissure-In-Ano): A Case Report. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(5), 891-895.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

A 36-year-old male patient came to the OPD complaining of hard stool, burning pain in the ano (during and after defecation), and per rectal bleeding during defecation form the previous month. A longitudinal tear at the anal canal midline posterior was seen during the clinical examination. This trauma was brought to anal canal by passages of hard stool a month ago. Parikartika, or Acute fissure in ano, the term is used to describe this condition. *USHIR Malahar has Vranaropaka, Dahashamaka properties*. Local application of *Ushir Malahar* was used in this case. *Malahar provides desired form and consistency to the ointment*. Ointment form is chosen because of its easy application on the fissure. A noticeable symptomatic relief after 15 days of treatment was seen.

KEYWORDS: *Parikartika, Ushir malahar.*

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda* condition associated with "Kartanvat Vedana" in the anal region is suggested by the word *Parikartika*.^[1] Brihatryi describes Parikartika as a consequence of certain

Panchakarm procedures, such as Vaman and Virechan Vyapad,^[2] Bastikarma Vyapad,^[3] and Vaatvyadhi Atisara Vyapad.^[4]

In modern science, it is described as a separate disease which is actually a linear tear in the anal canal that may stretch from the mucocutaneous junction to the dentate line having clinical symptoms of burning pain in ano and per rectal bleeding like streak of blood on stool mainly. It is caused most commonly by frequent Constipation and Diarrhoea.

Also sedentary habits, spicy foods and low fibre diet factors which causes and predisposes acute fissure (Parikartika). Anal canal being the site of many bacterias due to stool and hence a source for infection which can worsen a simple fissure. Fissure is treated by antibiotics, analgesics, laxatives, and local applications. If not relieved by this treatment, it can even lead to Fissure Bed Abscess and Fistula in ano which needs surgical treatment.

Parikartika is a longitudinal linear cut ulcer in ano so can be considered as Sadya Vrana. For Sadya Vrana treatment in Ayurveda Ropan Karma is chosen which is one of the sixty Upkrama of Vrana described by Acharya Sushruta. USHIR Malahar has Vranaropaka, Dahashamaka properties. Malahar provides desired form and consistency to the ointment. It releases medicament easily at application site. It should not produce irritation and sensitization of skin. The study is carried out to see the effect of Ushir Malahar and to find out successful alternative options of location application for Fissure in ano and significant results in symptoms.

Etiology and Pathophysiology

Ruksha, Tikshna Ahar taken by Saam and Mrudu Koshti person it causes Agni Dushti i.e. vitiation of Pitta takes place there is formation of Ama in Amashaya, this Aam Dosha along with vitiated Apan Vayu causes Grathit mala i.e. Malavasthambha in which mala became Shushka and hard. This produces trauma to Guda Pradesh during defecation and causes cutting pain in anus region ultimately results into *Parikartika* formation.

CASE STUDY

A 36 year Male Patient came in OPD with the symptoms of

- *Gudadaha* (Burning at Anal region)
- *Saraktmalpravrutti* (Bleeding during defecation)
- *Malavstambh* (Constipation)

History of present Illness

Patient was apparently well & Asymptomatic before 1 month ago. Later he developed hard stool. Due to which symptoms get developed and Gradually increases of *Guda Daha* (Burning at Anal region), *Guda Pradeshi Vedana* (Pain at anal region), *Saraktmalpravrutti* (Bleeding during defecation).

Past History HTN – No history in past DM - Non Diabetic TB - No History of TB BA - No History of Bronchial Asthma	Personal History Marital status - Married Tobacco - No History Alcohol - NAD Family History Father - HTN Mother – NAD
O/E (On Examination) GC - Fair Pulse - 72/min Bp - 110/70 mm/Hg Spo2 - 96% on RA RR - 16/ min Pallor - Absent Icterus - Absent	<i>Asthvidh Pariksha</i> <i>Nadi - Pitta kaphaj</i> <i>Mala - 1 times/day</i> <i>Mutra - 5-6 times/day</i> <i>Jiva -Niram</i> <i>Shabd - Prakrut</i> <i>Sparsh -Samshitoshna</i> <i>Druka - Prakrut</i> <i>Aakruti - Madhyam</i>
S/E (Systemic Examination) RS - AEBE Clear CVS - S1S2 NORMAL CNS - Conscious Oriented	

Local examination of *Gudavrana***INSPECTION**

Acute fissure seen at 6 O'clock position without fresh bleeding

Without sentinel tag

N/E/O -

- Ext haemorrhoid
- Ext fistulous track opening

DIGITAL RECTAL EXAMINATION

- Spasm present
- Tenderness present
- Proctoscopy not done due to spasm

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Presenting Complaints of Patient Treatment advice along with Pathyapathya and Sitz bath.

1. Daily local application of Ushir malahar – BD For 15 days.
2. Sitz bath with warm water.

Methods for Measurements

Subjective criteria

Gradaation for Symptom

1. Burning Pain

SR. NO	SIGN	GRADE
1.	NO PAIN	0
2.	Pain at the time of defecation and subside within 30 min	1
3.	Pain at the time of the defecation and persist for 30 min to 1 hour	2
4.	Continuous unbearable pain which persist more than 1 hour	3

2. PR BLEEDING

SR. NO	BLEEDING PER RECTUM	GRADE
1.	NIL	0
2.	1 to 5 drops	1
3.	5 to 10 drops	2
4.	> 10 drops	3

3. ULCER IN ANO

SR.NO	ULCER IN ANO	GRADE
1.	NO ULCER	0
2.	Clean and healthy ulcer	1
3.	Presence of ulcer with indurated margins without sentinel tag	2
4.	Presence of ulcer with indurated margins and slough without sentinel tag	3

RESULT

Sr. No	Symptom	Before Treatment	7 TH Day	15 TH Day
1.	Gudapradeshi Daha (Burning at Anal region)	3	1	0
2.	Saraktmalpravrutti (Bleeding during defecation)	2	1	0
3.	Ulcer in ano	2	1	0

DISCUSSION

Parikartika has vitiated *Apan Vayu*. Whenever Patient eat Hot, Spicy, Salty food aggravate the *Pitta Dosh*a. Dry, Less Fiber Diet, Less Drinking of Water this *hetu* aggravate the *Vata Dosh*a Increase the *Rukshata* (dryness) of stool. Pressure on anal canal due to Hard Stool Causes ulcer at Anal Opening and Symptoms Arises Mild to Severe burning pain with

bleeding during defecation. *Ushir Malahar* can be used in burning pain of fresh wound/ulcer. As it's contents have *Vranaropak* and *Dahashamak* properties. Due to these properties, it is useful in management of *Sadya Vran* hence acute fissure in ano (*Parikartika*).

CONCLUSION

From this Study It is clear that *Parikartika* Cases Can be managed with Ayurveda treatment in Initial Stage. We should try these *Shaman* treatments along with a sitz bath to quickly relieve Burning Pain. Change in lifestyle and healthy diet is very important in the management of *Parikartika* (Anal Fissure). This is a Single Case Study large Scale Case Study needed with this Ayurveda treatment.

REFERENCES

1. *Sushrut*, Acharya Priyavat Sharma, *Shushruta Samhita*, Uttarrardha, chikistastan 34/16, *Chaukhamba Prakashan*, 2017; 439.
2. *Shushrut*, Acharya Priyavat Sharma, *SUSHRUT SAMHITA*, 2nd part, Chikitsasthan. 34/21, *Chaukhamba Prakashan*, pg.no. 441 or Charak, Acharya Priyavat Sharma, *Charak Samhita*, 2nd part *Marathibhashantar*, *Charak Siddhisthan* 6/61-67 *Chaukhamba prakashan*, 910.
3. Charak, Acharya Priyavat Sharma, *Charak Samhita*, 2nd part *marathibhashantar*, *Charak Siddhisthan* 6/54-57, *Chaukhamba prakashan*, 910.
4. Charak, Acharya Priyavat Sharma, *Charak samhita*, 2nd part *marathibhashantar*, *Chikisathan* 19/5, *Chaukhamba prakashan*, 458.
5. Dr. G. Pandeya, *Bhavprakash Nighantu*, 2015, Varanasi, *Chokhamba publication*, *Gudduchyadi varga*, 314-315,3/43/94.